

DEVELOPMENT OF LOW NOISE AMPLIFIER (LNA) FOR 5G WI-FI
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Abstract. This paper presents a wideband low noise amplifier (LNA) implemented in 0.15 μ m InGaAs pHEMT technology low-noise 5.15GHz-5.925GHz frequency range LNA (low noise amplifier) for 5G Wi-Fi applications. The proposed circuit is fabricated using 0.15 μ m InGaAs pHEMT technology, and it is powered by 3.5V supply. To increase voltage gain and decrease power consumption, this circuit has common-source scheme, and it is optimized to decrease noise figure. Single stage common source and inductive source degeneration technique is also utilized to match the circuit to source impedance. The proposed LNA showed the total current of 15.4mA and the lowest noise figure of 0.77dB with high voltage gain of 16.27dB as compared to recently published results. It also showed the smallest chip area of 0.64 \times 1.07mm², and the size of the core cell of 0.44 \times 0.81mm² without pads as compared to recently reported results. We expect that the proposed LNA is suitable for GHz-band 5G Wi-Fi Applications.

Keywords: Noise Figure, 0.15 μ m, LNA (low noise amplifier), 5G Wi-Fi applications

1. INTRODUCTION

The first active amplification component of a receiver is a LNA. The main function of LNA is to amplify the signal to suppress the noise of subsequent stage while adding as little noise as possible. The performance of RF receiver is significantly influenced by the LNA. Operating frequency also depends on the RF filter used in front of LNA. They offer a good gain and low noise figure, but they are expensive and cannot be integrated easily. As the new technology evolved, we successfully researched the feasibility of the new WIN technologies in RF circuit designs. WIN devices translated into low noise figure and higher gain. Latest WIN technologies showed to be a strong not only in terms of cost and integration, but also in terms of high performance.

Inductive source generation low noise amplifier provides best noise performance and gain. The LNA is one the most important block in transceiver used in wireless communication system [1-5].

Power consumption plays an important role in any wireless communication system. Most recent LNAs for 5GHz band used the inductive source degeneration architecture. This architecture has advantages of simultaneous input and power matching, reduced input and output interaction with reducing miller effects which results in better stability.

IEEE 802.11ac standard is known as 5G Wi-Fi. Modern Wi-Fi technology uses 5.15GHz and 5.95GHz frequencies. The design of LNA is mainly important in the performance of the overall receiver chain. The noise performance of the LNA should be critical because the same noise is amplified in the succeeding stages. To control the noise in the subsequent stages, LNA gain should be very high. The design of LNA should balance the Gain, Input impedance, Noise Figure and Power Consumption.

A couple of CS stages are stacked to share the current, and the double transformers are implemented as an RF signal path between the CS stages to improve the gain and stability.

This paper presents a wideband low-noise 5.15GHz-5.925GHz LNA for 5G Wi-Fi applications. The proposed circuit is fabricated using 0.15 μ m InGaAs pHEMT technology and it is powered by 3.5V supply. To increase voltage gain, this circuit has common-source scheme, and it is optimized to decrease noise figure. Single stage inductive source degeneration technique is also utilized to match the circuit to source impedance.

2. CIRCUIT DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

2.1 Overview of 5G Wi-Fi applications

Different lines are used to carry wireless internet. One band is 2.4GHz, while another is 5GHz. Dual band modems and routers have both 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz, whereas single band modems only have 2.4 GHz. This can be compared to a two-lane road. As a result, certain devices can concurrently use the 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz paths.

The issue does not end with a single tape. Old internet standards such as B and G can only operate at 2.4 GHz. 802.11n is today's minimal base speed standard, which can be supplied at 2.4GHz and 5GHz. However, as technology advances, the 802.11ac standard has entered our life. We have dual band and AC standards when we utilize an up-to-date and high-quality modem and router. The 2.4GHz frequency is more widely utilized than the 5GHz frequency. As a result of channel overcrowding, greater interference occurs during data transmission. The 5GHz frequency band has 23 channels, whereas the 2.4GHz range has only three. As a result, folks who utilize a lot of Wi-Fi devices should use the 5GHz frequency.

The main distinction between the two is their speed. 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi may support up to 450 Mbps or 600 Mbps under optimum conditions, depending on the router class. Wi-Fi at 5 GHz can support up to 1300 Mbps. Because the 5GHz band is less congested, you should get more stable connections. You will also notice faster speeds. Shorter waves, such as those employed by the 5 GHz band, have a lower ability to penetrate walls and solid objects. Its effective range is also shorter than that of the 2.4GHz band.

Fig. 1. Concept of Wi-Fi application.

2.2. Design of the proposed LNA

In this work, a single-stage single-end LNA is designed using an optimized resistor bias circuit and implemented by a standard WIN 0.15 μ m InGaAs pHEMT process provided by a commercial foundry. This technology offers 9 metal layers, named M1 to M9 from bottom to top. The single-end topology is used to avoid lossy baluns and extra power consumption.

To meet the requirements of noise figure and gain, a common-source (CS) amplifier is used as the first stage to keep the circuit low-noise, followed by a common-source amplifier to boost gain. Figure 2 depicts a schematic of a proposed single-stage single-end LNA.

Fig. 2. Single stage common-source LNA

As shown in Figure 2, the size of transistor M1 is carefully selected through simulation. Furthermore, proper biasing is used to ensure that the circuit maintains low noise and suitable gain. To reduce resistive loss, we used transmission-line (TL) inductors and interconnection-lines (ILs). Moreover, proper biasing is chosen to make the circuit keep low-noise and higher gain. Capacitor C1 is used to block the DC signal and transmission lines TL2 and TL5 are introduced to get Noise and Input Matching. C2, C3 are bypass capacitors for leaching the clutter signal (unwanted signal) from supply source.

To reduce NF due to the CS stage, but a large inductor and bypass capacitor were required.

In this project, we used single stage LNA to achieve high gain, and low noise figure. To reduce the power consumption, it uses biasing circuit itself to supply Vgs voltage at the gate of CPW1 transistor. Vds=3.5 V and Vgs=0.7 V.

The MIM capacitors are used for high quality factors and the resistors of tantalum nitride thin film are used. Large on-chip bypass capacitors are placed between each VDD and ground. The die occupies 0.64×1.07mm² including pads and 0.41×0.81mm² without pads.

Fig. 3. Die photograph of the proposed LNA.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In analog and RF blocks, high output power with high efficiency is desirable, but with the above-mentioned limitations on the recent technologies, achieving these goals requires special attention on the designing circuits with new techniques and topologies. From Figs. 2 and 3, the proposed LNA showed total dc current of 15.4mA at 3.5V supply, so we obtained the lowest power consumption of 53.9mW as compared to conventional results [3-6].

Fig. 4 shows (a) input return loss S₁₁, and (b) output return loss S₂₂. Input and output impedance matching is so important to obtain low input and output return losses. Ideal input and output impedances of the amplifier must have 45~50Ω at the operation frequency.

Fig. 4. (a) Input Return loss S_{11} and (b) Output Return loss S_{22}

Voltage gain is very important parameter in GHz-band LNA. Fig. 5 shows voltage gain (S_{21}). As shown in Fig. 5, the proposed LNA showed very high voltage gain of 16.2dB at the operation frequency of 5.25GHz as compared to conventional results [3-6].

Fig. 5. S_{21} .

Fig. 6. Noise figure.

To verify performance of the proposed LNA, we carried out simulations and layout using ADS tools. The S-parameter and noise figure of the proposed LNA is shown in Fig. 4, Fig. 5, and Fig. 6.

The proposed LNA showed the total current of 15.4mA, the highest voltage gain of 17dB, and the lowest noise figure of 0.92dB as compared to conventional results [6-8]. It also has the smallest die size $0.41 \times 0.81 \text{mm}^2$ without pads as compared to recently reported research results [6-8].

In this paper, we proposed low-noise 5.15GHz-5.95GHz LNA for 5G Wi-Fi application. This circuit is implemented in WIN $0.15 \mu\text{m}$ InGaAs pHEMT process. To increase voltage gain and decrease power consumption, we utilized inductive source degeneration technique. The LNA was optimized by minimization of the inherent LNA noise added to the desired or wanted signal during the process of amplification to reduce noise figure. The proposed LNA showed total dc current of 15.4mA at 3.5V supply, so we obtained the power consumption of 53.9mW as compared to conventional results. It also showed the lowest noise figure of 0.92dB, high voltage gain of 17dB, good S-parameter results and small die size $0.41 \times 0.81 \text{mm}^2$ without pads as compared to recently reported research results.

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